

Green leafhopper (*Nephotettix virescens* Dist.) resistance ratings of rice varieties with different resistance genes, Coimbatore, India.

Variety	Resistance gene ^a	Damage rating ^b					
		6 DI	7 DI	8 DI	9 DI	10 DI	11 DI
Pankhari 203	<i>Glh 1</i>	9.0 c	9.0 d	9.0 e	9.0 e	9.0 d	9.0 d
ASD 7	<i>Glh 2</i>	2.3 a	3.0 ab	5.0 bcd	5.7 cde	7.0 cd	7.7 d
IR8	<i>Glh 3</i>	1.7 a	3.7 b	5.0 bcd	6.3 de	7.0 cd	1.0 cd
Ptb 8	<i>glh 4</i>	1.0 a	2.3 ab	2.3 abc	3.0 abc	3.7 ab	3.1 ab
ASD 8	<i>Glh 5</i>	1.0 a	3.0 ab	3.7 abcd	5.0 bcd	5.7 bc	7.0 d
TAPL 196	<i>Glh 6</i>	1.7 a	1.7 ab	3.0 abcd	3.7 abcd	3.7 ab	5.0 bc
Moddai Karuppan	<i>Glh 7</i>	1.0 a	1.0 a	1.0 a	1.0 a	1.7 a	2.3 a
IR20	<i>Glh 3</i>	1.7 a	3.7 b	5.7 cde	6.3 de	7.7 cd	7.7 d
IR24	NA	2.3 a	3.7 b	5.7 cde	7.0 de	7.7 cd	7.7 d
IR26	NA	1.0 a	1.0 a	1.7 ab	2.3 ab	3.0 a	3.0 ab
IR36	<i>Glh 6</i>	1.7 a	1.7 ab	1.7 ab	1.7 ab	1.7 a	1.7 a
IR42	NA	1.7 a	1.7 ab	2.3 abc	3.0 abc	3.0 a	3.0 ab
IR50	NA	1.0 a	1.7 ab	1.7 ab	1.7 ab	1.7 a	1.7 a
IR54	NA	1.7 a	1.7 ab	3.0 abcd	2.3 ab	2.3 a	2.3 a
IR29 (resistant check)	NA	1.0 a	1.7 ab	1.7 ab	1.7 ab	2.3 a	3.0 ab
TN1 (susceptible check)	-	5.0 b	6.3 c	7.0 de	8.3 e	8.3 d	9.0 d

^aNA = not ascertained. ^bScored by the Standard Evaluation System for Rice. Within a column, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level. DI = days after infestation.

susceptible.

Genes *Glh 1*, *Glh 2*, *Glh 3*, *glh 4*, and *Glh 5* were identified at IRRI using a Philippine population of *N. virescens*

Genes *Glh 6* and *Glh 7* were identified in Bangladesh.

Pankhari 203, which is susceptible at Coimbatore, is highly resistant in the

Philippines. On the other hand, Moddai Karuppan is moderately susceptible in the Philippines but is highly resistant at Coimbatore and Bangladesh. ■

Resistance of rice cultivars and wild rices to thrips

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Among yield nursery seedlings of rice cultivars and wild rices screened for thrips *Baliothrips biformis* (Bagnall) resistance, Ptb 33, BG379-1, and Kalubalawee Sudurvi 305 were highly resistant. Gangala, Utri Rajappan, BG367-1, BG367-9, BG379-5, OB678, and IR17494-32-1-1-3-2 were resistant.

Wild rices found resistant to thrips at Coimbatore, India.

IRRI accession number	Name	Origin	Rating
103437	<i>O. glaberrima</i>	Senegal	1
103443	<i>O. glaberrima</i>	Senegal	1
103831	<i>O. sariva</i> f. <i>spontanea</i>	Bangladesh	1
103836	<i>O. nivara</i>	Bangladesh	1
101171	<i>O. eichingeri</i>	Tanzania	3
101510	<i>O. nivara</i>	India	3
101993	<i>O. rufipogon</i> / <i>O. nivara</i>	Sri Lanka	3
103438	<i>O. glaberrima</i>	Senegal	3
103791	<i>O. nivara</i> / <i>O. sativa</i>	Venezuela	3
103826	<i>O. sativa</i> f. <i>spontanea</i>	Bangladesh	3
103849	<i>O. perennis</i>	India	3

Eleven wild rices were resistant (see table). Varieties BG367-1, BG367-9, BG379-1, BG379-5, IR17494-32-1-1-3-2, and OB678 also were resistant to brown planthopper. ■

Reaction of gall midge-resistant cultures at Warangal, India

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The Agricultural Research Station, Warangal, India, collaborated with the All India Cooperative Rice Improvement Project and IRRI in a study to identify gall midge biotypes and their distribution in India.

Field screening was conducted from 1977 to 1980. Observations on midge incidence were made on hill and tiller

Call midge biotype collaborative study, Warangal, India, and IRRI, 1978-80.

Culture	Hills infested (%)			Reaction ^a
	1978	1979	1980	
<i>Leuang 152</i>				
Leuang 152	0	0	0	R
CR95-JR-46-1	0	0	0	R
CR95-JR-214	0	14	0	MR
<i>Ptb</i>				
Ptb 10	0	— ^b	—	R
Ptb 18	0	0	4	R
Ptb 21	0	0	4	R
CR157-392-4	4	0	—	R
CR94-13	5	4	—	R
IR36	0	2	22	S
<i>Eswarakora</i>				
W1263	0	0	2	R
Kakatiya	0	0	0	R

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